

From strain to stress using full-field data: Computationally efficient stress reconstruction

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Abstract. Conventional stress reconstruction based on full-field strain measurements presents a major computational burden, especially when using standard implicit stress integration methods. This presents a notable challenge for inverse identification methods used to characterize the plasticity of metallic materials, particularly those reliant on stress reconstruction, such as the nonlinear sensitivity-based Virtual Fields Method (VFM). To reduce the computational effort, the full-field strain data are usually spatially and temporally down-sampled. However, for metals subject to nonlinear strain paths, this practice can lead to errors in the resulting stress states and compromise the accuracy of the nonlinear VFM. In this work, we introduce a highly efficient explicit stress reconstruction algorithm to reduce the computational challenges of repeated stress reconstruction which can be utilized in inverse identification methods such as nonlinear VFM.

Introduction

The development of optical technologies has opened up new possibilities to characterize the behavior of materials in solid mechanics. The use of 3D scanners and cameras has enabled precise measurements of body displacements and deformations under load. The ability to accurately track and quantify displacements and strains allows engineers to assess material behavior and make informed design decisions. Digital image correlation (DIC) is one of the most commonly used techniques for calculating strain. In this method, sequentially captured images are processed to extract valuable information that facilitates the study of local behavior and global responses in structures. In addition, DIC can be used in real time and offers the possibility to monitor structural responses under dynamic loading conditions. This feature makes DIC a powerful tool for various applications, including material testing, structural analyses and product development.

Despite significant advances in metrology that enable precise measurements of the full evolution of the strain field during loading, the challenge of efficiently reconstructing the corresponding evolution of the stress field in real time remains. In the case of linear elastic materials, the reconstruction of the stress field from the strain field can be performed seamlessly. However, in the case of nonlinear material behavior, such as plasticity, the mechanical response depends on the loading path and is described by algebraic differential equations. The effective solution of these equations to obtain the stress state for a given time frame remains a challenge.

State of the art

The effectiveness of stress reconstruction algorithms is of crucial importance in today's applications. The need arises, for example, in materials testing, where inverse identification methods are used to determine material behavior from measured heterogeneous strain data. An effective stress integration algorithm is essential in this context to ensure accurate and timely results.

In other words, the development of full-field measurement techniques which provide a wealth of information has played a crucial role in the development of novel identification strategies. These strategies aim to reduce the calibration effort compared to conventional material testing. Information-rich experiments take advantage of the heterogeneity of deformation to determine multiple material model parameters simultaneously. Most of these experiments use DIC to capture heterogeneous strain fields and subject them to an inverse identification process. This approach has unlocked the potential for inverse material characterization and led to the development of new identification methods, such as the Virtual Field Method (VFM) [1], the Equilibrium Gap Method (EGM) [2] and the Constitutive Equation Gap Method (CEGM) [3], Reciprocity Gap Method (RGM) [4], Finite Element Model Updating (FEMU) [5], Integrated Mechanical Image Correlation (I-MIC) [6], Integrated Digital Image Correlation (I-DIC) [7] and various combined theoretical/experimental approaches such as [8], [9].

Initially, these methods were applied to elasticity problems, but today, the most commonly used methods for plasticity problems are FEMU and VFM. FEMU is a user-friendly method that uses an optimization algorithm to minimize the difference between measured and computed Finite Element Analysis (FEA) results. It has been used to identify parameters for various plasticity models, such as Hill48 [10] and YLD2000-2d [11]. VFM, on the other hand, is based on the principle of virtual work and force equilibrium. It was initially used to determine elastic properties [12], but later, the method was also successfully applied to plasticity problems [13], [14].

Both FEMU and VFM suffer from certain drawbacks that prevent them from gaining wider acceptance in the industrial engineering community. Inverse identification with FEMU is extremely computationally intensive for plasticity models because the optimization algorithm requires the results of the FEM for all material points in a region of interest (ROI) in each iteration, as well as repeating all FEM analyses for perturbed values of all model parameters in each iteration. Each FEM analysis also involves equilibrium iterations, and for each iteration of the FEM analysis, the complete stress field needs to be computed. VFM is much more computationally efficient for elasticity, but becomes computationally intensive for plasticity, where the stress field must also be reconstructed at each iteration.

As an example, Lattanzi et al. [15] reported that the computational time for the VFM ranges from 11 to 83 minutes on an Intel Xeon CPU E5-1650 v2 @ 3.50 GHz and 128 GB of RAM. However, it's important to note that the computational time can vary greatly depending on various factors such as the size of the model, the complexity of material behavior, and the computational resources available. Despite these variations, the superiority of VFM over FEMU has been demonstrated by Rahmani et al. [16] and Zhang et al. [17], who reported that VFM is 125 times faster than conventional FEMU for their specific application. In a study by Marek et al. [18], the identification time was found to range from 4 to 278 hours, depending on the material model and identification algorithm used. They concluded that the stress reconstruction algorithm was the main limiting factor in efficiency and suggested replacing the implicit stress reconstruction algorithm with a more efficient explicit one, as proposed by Rossi et al. [19]. A similar conclusion was found in [20], where the computational time for VFM was reported to range from 25 to 35 minutes.

As presented, both methods, FEMU and VFM, utilize the inhomogeneous strain field processed by DIC, but they face efficiency issues when it comes to reconstructing the stress state from a given strain field. This limitation hampers the efficiency of material identification when a large number of strain increments are used to describe the loading path.

In this paper, our primary objective is to improve the efficiency of conventional stress reconstruction algorithms commonly employed in inverse material identification methods, such as the Virtual Fields Method (VFM), while addressing and overcoming the limitations inherent in traditional integration techniques. Dense temporal sampling drastically increases the

computational cost. Such a situation is forcing to reconsider the stress reconstruction algorithms: are the algorithms known for stress updating in FEM also optimal for stress reconstruction associated with full field strain measurements? Not necessarily; a study by Rossi et al. [21] found that there is an approximated method for stress reconstruction from measured strain data that does not require iteration and is capable of handling large increments.

The stress update algorithms used in FEM are typically based on unconditionally stable implicit integration methods, with the implicit backward Euler scheme being the most widely used approach. This method is widely used in commercial software and among researchers for various models (referenced in [22]). However, when using implicit integration for stress reconstruction in each time frame, the computation time depends directly on the number of time frames, creating a dilemma of how many time frames should be considered to achieve satisfactory accuracy. There is currently no clear answer to this question in the field of plasticity.

The main message we want to convey is that the dilemma of determining the number of time frames for stress path integration can be resolved by using explicit schemes. These explicit schemes solve the problem by using numerous, computationally effective increments, and if the increments are small due to the algorithm itself, this integration approach can cover all recorded time frames, eliminating the need to decide on the amount of time frames to consider.

In the plasticity domain, explicit schemes have a low reputation due to their conditional stability and permanent drift. However, in [23], [24], we presented an explicit integration scheme Next Increment Corrects Error (NICE), which is suitable for explicit FEM and does not produce permanent drift. The scheme has been further developed for higher order accuracy [25] and extended to be suitable for implicit FEM, integrating with the maximum possible stable subincrements and preserving accuracy within each increment [26]. Guaranteed stability, accuracy, and fast computation are crucial for efficient stress reconstruction from strain data.

In this paper, we present an adaptation of the NICE algorithm to be used with strain field data obtained through image processing. This adaptation is independent of the number of frames, allowing for full use of full-field data. The proposed algorithm differs from conventional stress reconstruction algorithms as it possesses the necessary properties for inverse identification.

Methodology

In this paper we propose a methodology to meet the main objectives of examining the influence of strain temporal down-sampling on the stress reconstruction and avoiding the efficiency bottleneck of conventional stress reconstruction algorithms. We conducted a simple synthetic test, an open-hole test experiment, which is commonly used in heterogeneous specimen testing. The experiment is mimicked in ABAQUS/Standard, from which the displacement field is extracted in each increment for each nodal position in FE mesh. In the next step, the extracted displacement field is used to numerically deform a reference speckle pattern, which is used to generate synthetically deformed images. These numerically deformed images are afterwards passed into DIC software to process the corresponding strain fields. In the final step, the extracted strain data is used for stress computation using both conventional Implicit Radial Mapping Algorithm (IRMA) and NICE algorithms for different sets of strain increments. For instance, the whole strain path can be integrated at each image frame or using only a selected number of frames. The difference in stress error due to the strain path approximation is monitored. This scenario is commonly encountered in real DIC application where numerous images representing incremental strain evolution are available, but stress reconstruction algorithms like VFM do not consider all increments due to efficiency limitations.

Finally, we analyze the efficiency of the IRMA and NICE algorithms when dealing with the entire strain path divided into different numbers of strain increments used in the integration process. The NICE algorithm, being explicit in nature, is expected to offer higher computational efficiency.

Theoretical background

Kinematics of incremental finite deformation. In finite element computations, the equations of motion are solved numerically to obtain the nodal displacements at the end of each increment. To achieve full agreement with the kinematics of commercial FEM codes (e.g. ABAQUS) in our external code, we follow the same principles here. This step is crucial to accurately analyze the effects of the strain path when only a selected number of increments are considered in the stress integration algorithm. In other words, the input of the external code, which uses either the IRMA or the NICE algorithm, is based on the known stress state at the beginning of the increment $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^n$ and the incremental deformation gradient $\hat{\mathbf{F}} = \mathbf{F}^{n+1}(\mathbf{F}^n)^{-1}$, where \mathbf{F}^n and \mathbf{F}^{n+1} correspond to deformation gradients at the beginning and at the end of the increment with respect to the initial configuration, respectively. As implemented ABAQUS [27], a constant midpoint velocity gradient $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{L}(t + \Delta t/2)$ and incremental deformation gradient $\hat{\mathbf{F}}$ are related by $\mathbf{L} = 2(\hat{\mathbf{F}} - \mathbf{1})(\hat{\mathbf{F}} + \mathbf{1})^{-1}$, where $\mathbf{1}$ presents second order identity tensor. According to Hughes and Winget [27], a constant strain increment tensor can be computed as $\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = 1/2(\mathbf{L} + \mathbf{L}^T)$ and the incremental rotation tensor as $\mathbf{R} = (\mathbf{1} - 1/2 \boldsymbol{\omega})^{-1}(\mathbf{1} + 1/2 \boldsymbol{\omega})$, with a spin tensor $\boldsymbol{\omega} = 1/2(\mathbf{L} - \mathbf{L}^T)$. According to this procedure, the total strain is computed by approximatively integrating the strain rate according to the midpoint scheme. Since the components of the total strain and stress tensors are related to the fixed coordinate basis, the Hughes-Winget method is used to account for rigid body rotations by computing $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^n \leftarrow \mathbf{R} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^n \mathbf{R}^T$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^n \leftarrow \mathbf{R} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^n \mathbf{R}^T$ before passing the states to the stress integration algorithm.

Stress integration. In plasticity, the evolution of stress tensor is conventionally calculated from the strain tensor evolution using radial return integration algorithm [28], which is implemented in FEM using iterative method [29]. Stress reconstruction from a measured strain field is commonly performed using the IRMA algorithm [22], based on the radial return algorithm. However, recent advances in the field have led to the development of non-iterative stress integration methods. Rossi et al. [21] proposed an approximation of the stresses without time-consuming iterations, while Yoon and Barlat [30] introduced a method that redefines the effective plastic strain increment. These approaches focus on approximating the stress state with large increments and do not address the issue of inaccurate integration caused by the coarseness of time integration and the acquired full-field data. In contrast, the algorithm described here integrates the entire strain path in small but fast increments.

The NICE stress integration algorithm is based on the work presented in [26], where we introduced an explicit scheme for integrating plasticity models that is also suitable for implicit FEM with large increments. The algorithm's stability is conditional and it marches with the maximum possible stable subincrements. Unlike other explicit schemes, the NICE scheme does not generate permanent drift from the consistency condition, making it a promising choice for stress reconstruction from measured strain fields. The NICE scheme has been successfully applied to various rate-independent plasticity models, including models with inhomogeneous yield functions, such as the Gurson model. Its accuracy, simple expressions, and fast calculations make it a highly attractive option for stress reconstruction from a measured strain field.

A comprehensive explanation of the scheme is provided in [26], which includes the formulation for the plane stress state. Although the algorithm is versatile and can be applied to different models, the formulation is simplified to von Mises plasticity with isotropic hardening for brevity.

The variables in the plane stress state von Mises plasticity model are updated using the following expressions: $\Phi = \sigma_{\text{eq}} - \sigma_Y = 0$ represents the yield condition with $\sigma_{\text{eq}}^2 = \sigma_{11}^2 + \sigma_{22}^2 + \sigma_{11}\sigma_{22} + 3\sigma_{12}^2$ being the equivalent stress and σ_Y the current yield stress. The components of the stress deviator are defined as $s_{11} = \sigma_{11} - \sigma_H$, $s_{22} = \sigma_{22} - \sigma_H$, $s_{33} = \sigma_{33} - \sigma_H$, $s_{12} = \sigma_{12}$, where

$\sigma_H = (\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22})/3$ is the hydrostatic stress. The elastic properties are defined as $C_{dia} = E/(1 - \nu^2)$, $C_{offdia} = C_{dia}\nu$, $\mu = E/2/(1 + \nu)$, $C_{3311} = C_{3322} = C_{offdia}(1 - \nu)/(1 - 2\nu)$, $C_{3333} = C_{3311}(\nu^{-1} - 1)$, where E , ν and μ are the elastic modulus, the Poisson's coefficient and the shear modulus, respectively. The hardening is described by the hardening modulus $H = d\sigma_Y/d\varepsilon_{eq}^p$ based on the given hardening curve.

The algorithm can be outlined as follows:

1. Initialize the elastic constants E , ν , μ , C_{dia} , C_{offdia} , C_{3311} , C_{3322} , C_{3333} at the beginning of the step and set $n = 0$.
2. Initialize variables at the beginning of the n^{th} increment $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^n = \{\sigma_{11}^n, \sigma_{22}^n, \sigma_{12}^n\}$, σ_{eq}^n , σ_Y^n , $(\varepsilon_{eq}^p)^n$, H^n , Φ^n and compute $\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \{\Delta\varepsilon_{11}, \Delta\varepsilon_{22}, \Delta\varepsilon_{12}\}$ from deformation gradients \mathbf{F}^n and \mathbf{F}^{n+1} (Eq. 3)
3. Compute trial stress state ($\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{tr} \leftarrow \boldsymbol{\sigma}^n + \Delta\boldsymbol{\sigma}$) via $\Delta\sigma_{11} = C_{dia}\Delta\varepsilon_{11} + C_{offdia}\Delta\varepsilon_{22}$, $\Delta\sigma_{22} = C_{offdia}\Delta\varepsilon_{11} + C_{dia}\Delta\varepsilon_{22}$, $\Delta\sigma_{12} = 2\mu\Delta\varepsilon_{12}$, compute σ_{eq}^{tr} , and Φ^{tr} .
4. If $\Phi^{tr} < 0$:
 - elastic update: $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{n+1} \leftarrow \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{tr}$, $\Phi^{n+1} \leftarrow \Phi^{tr} \Rightarrow$ go to Step 2, next increment $n \leftarrow n + 1$
 - else
 - elastoplastic update \Rightarrow proceed with Step 5
5. Project the stress state onto the yield surface by $\beta = -\Phi^n/(\Phi^{tr} - \Phi^n)$, update the elastic stress state: $\boldsymbol{\sigma} \leftarrow \boldsymbol{\sigma}^n + \beta\Delta\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, subtract the elastic update: $\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \leftarrow (1 - \beta)\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$, $\Delta\boldsymbol{\sigma} \leftarrow (1 - \beta)\Delta\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and compute σ_{eq} , Φ , $\mathbf{s} = \{s_{11}, s_{22}, s_{33}, s_{12}\}$.
6. Compute the number of subincrements by $N_{sub} = \text{floor}((1 - \beta)V_1/(\frac{\sigma_Y}{27\mu}V_2 - \Phi) + 1)$, where $V_1 = 3(s_{11}\Delta\sigma_{11} + s_{22}\Delta\sigma_{22} + 2s_{12}\Delta\sigma_{12})/(2\sigma_{eq})$ and $V_2 = 3\mu + H - 9\mu s_{33}^2(1 - 2\nu)/(2\sigma_{eq}^2(1 - \nu))$.
7. Subincrementation and compute σ_{eq} , Φ , \mathbf{s} , H , V_3 , $V_4 \Rightarrow$ Repeat this step N_{sub} -times
 - $\Delta\lambda = (\Phi + V_1/N_{sub})/V_2$, $V_3 = 3\mu/\sigma_{eq}$, $V_4 = s_{33}\nu/(1 - \nu)$
 - $\sigma_{11} \leftarrow \sigma_{11} + \Delta\sigma_{11}/N_{sub} - V_3(s_{11} - V_4)\Delta\lambda$
 - $\sigma_{22} \leftarrow \sigma_{22} + \Delta\sigma_{22}/N_{sub} - V_3(s_{22} - V_4)\Delta\lambda$
 - $\sigma_{12} \leftarrow \sigma_{12} + \Delta\sigma_{12}/N_{sub} - V_3s_{12}\Delta\lambda$
 - $\varepsilon_{eq}^p \leftarrow \varepsilon_{eq}^p + \Delta\lambda$
 - $\sigma_Y \leftarrow \sigma_Y + H\Delta\lambda$
8. Update variables for the next increment $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{n+1} \leftarrow \boldsymbol{\sigma}$, $\sigma_Y^{n+1} \leftarrow \sigma_Y$, $\Phi^{n+1} \leftarrow \Phi$, $(\varepsilon_{eq}^p)^{n+1} \leftarrow \varepsilon_{eq}^p \Rightarrow$ go to Step 2, next increment $n \leftarrow n + 1$

The number of arithmetic operations at each increment is small. There are no iterations, the scheme marches through the integration path. The size of the subincrements is usually smaller than the DIC sampling due to the stability constraint. Therefore, it is meaningless for the presented algorithm to reduce the number of time frames considered, as substepping is activated anyway for large increments; the algorithm integrates the stress path in approximately the same total number of subincrements, regardless of the time frames considered. This means that the computation time is also independent of the DIC sampling (i.e., the number of time frames measured), so it does not matter how many time frames are considered. In order to use all measured data and accurately track the load path, all sampled time frames should be considered, and the presented algorithm will always have the same computational cost for any given sampling.

Demonstration case via synthetic experiment

In an actual experiment, the deformation gradient is sampled using DIC. To assess the performance of both stress integration algorithms when fed with DIC-sampled deformation gradients, we devised a Digital Virtual Twin (DVT) of the open hole tension test using the FEDEF module of

the MatchID software. In this module, a speckle pattern is numerically deformed based on the nodal displacements generated by ABAQUS/Standard. Given that the ABAQUS simulation was divided into 300 frames, 300 deformed images were created. The optimized speckle pattern presented in [31] was used in this study. The 300 images were then post-processed using local DIC to reconstruct the deformation gradient field in each image. We should mention that in this case the location of the ROI was chosen as a function of plastic deformation occurring in the open hole tensile test. For this purpose, we avoid the regions which do not undergo plastic straining. In addition, we only consider trustworthy DIC data hence discard data affected by edge effects. In Fig. 1 the location of the considered is depicted, where 1 px 10 μm , which corresponds to typical DIC settings.

Figure 1: The Digital Virtual Twin. (a) a numerical reference speckle pattern used to generate synthetically deformed images based on the finite element simulation of the open hole tensile test. (b)-(d) reference stress field solution computed by ABAQUS/Standard.

During the procedure, we extracted the deformation gradient \mathbf{F} for all frames and points within the ROI from the DIC analysis and repeated the process. The deformation gradient was then used as input for the external stress reconstruction software utilizing both the IRMA algorithm and the NICE algorithm. Fig. 2a through Fig. 2f display the distributions of the stress components, which were computed by IRMA and NICE from the spatiotemporal distribution of the deformation gradient \mathbf{F} . From the figure it can be observed that both algorithms produce a closely matching solution. By comparing the field distributions with the referential stress state shown in the Fig. 1a to Fig. 1d, it becomes evident that solutions by both numerical algorithms also match with the solution computed by ABAQUS. Hence, it can be stated that the kinematics are adequately captured by the adopted DIC settings. Naturally, the smoothness of the numerical stress fields shown in Fig. 1 cannot be completely reproduced by the reconstructed “experimental” stress fields.

Figure 2: Comparison of referential and DIC-based reconstructed stress components: While the 1st row represents the stress fields computed from the reconstructed kinematic field using DIC by IRMA, the second row presents the solution obtained by NICE using the same procedure. Both schemes produce closely matching results.

The blue and red curves in Fig. 3 relate to different number of frames used in stress reconstruction algorithm. It can be observed that time consumption increases exponentially with the number of frames for IRMA algorithm, but remains constant for the NICE algorithm. Moreover, we should mention that for both algorithms the consumed time increases proportionally with the number of data points – the higher the number of points, the higher the time consumption. Finally, as shown, the NICE scheme significantly outperforms the IRMA scheme when a large number of images is used. In other words, with the NICE, the experimentalist can achieve the same stress reconstruction accuracy at a computational cost which is independent of the considered number of frames. The speedup factor of the NICE compared to the IRMA in this particular case is approximately 10. The more images are considered (e.g. to capture highly nonlinear strain paths or material behavior), the higher the speedup factor will be. As such, it must be emphasized that the speedup factor highly depends on the considered problem. In this regard, for MT2.0 applications requiring repetitive stress reconstructions (e.g. nonlinear VFM), we consider the NICE scheme to be a breakthrough in terms of computational efficiency.

Figure 3: Total CPU time for all plastic updates of stress reconstruction using IRMA and NICE algorithms for varying number of frames. The relationship between the number of frames, number of data points and CPU time is presented in a Log-Log scale. As presented the CPU time increases exponentially for with the number of frames for IRMA as for NICE algorithm in remains constant, resulting in a speed-up factor of 10 for 300 frames.

Summary

To summarize, we have introduced a highly efficient explicit stress reconstruction algorithm based on the NICE scheme to reduce the computational challenges of repeated stress reconstruction within inverse identification methods such as the nonlinear VFM. The main findings of our study are as follows:

- The proposed method for stress reconstruction shows comparable accuracy to the conventional fully implicit return mapping algorithm.
- In contrast to the fully implicit approach, our method maintains consistent computational efficiency regardless of the number of images used to derive the strain fields by DIC.
- Specifically applied to the open-hole tensile test problem, our stress reconstruction method achieves a remarkable speed-up factor of 10 compared to the traditional fully implicit return mapping algorithm. It is important to emphasize that the observed speed-up factor depends on the nonlinearity of the problem. This indicates the potential for even greater speed up in scenarios with pronounced nonlinearity, intricate anisotropic plasticity and nonlinear loading conditions.

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Disclaimer

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References

- [1] M. Grédiac, F. Pierron, S. Avril, E. Toussaint, and M. Rossi, “Virtual Fields Method,” in *Full-Field Measurements and Identification in Solid Mechanics*, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2012, pp. 301–330. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118578469.ch11>
- [2] D. Claire, F. Hild, and S. Roux, “A finite element formulation to identify damage fields: the equilibrium gap method,” *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, vol. 61, no. 2, pp. 189–208. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.1057>
- [3] E. Pagnacco, A. Moreau, and D. Lemosse, “Inverse strategies for the identification of elastic and viscoelastic material parameters using full-field measurements,” *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, vol. 452–453, pp. 737–745. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msea.2006.10.122>
- [4] H. D. Bui, A. Constantinescu, and H. Maigre, “Numerical identification of linear cracks in 2D elastodynamics using the instantaneous reciprocity gap,” *Inverse Probl.*, vol. 20, no. 4, p. 993. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0266-5611/20/4/001>
- [5] F. Mathieu, H. Leclerc, F. Hild, and S. Roux, “Estimation of Elastoplastic Parameters via Weighted FEMU and Integrated-DIC,” *Exp. Mech.*, vol. 55, no. 1, pp. 105–119. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11340-014-9888-9>
- [6] J. Réthoré, Muhibullah, T. Elguedj, M. Coret, P. Chaudet, and A. Combescure, “Robust identification of elasto-plastic constitutive law parameters from digital images using 3D kinematics,” *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 73–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2012.09.002>
- [7] A. P. Ruybalid, J. P. M. Hoefnagels, O. van der Sluis, and M. G. D. Geers, “Comparison of the identification performance of conventional FEM updating and integrated DIC,” *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, vol. 106, no. 4, pp. 298–320. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.5127>
- [8] S. Coppeters and T. Kuwabara, “Identification of Post-Necking Hardening Phenomena in Ductile Sheet Metal,” *Exp. Mech.*, vol. 54, no. 8, pp. 1355–1371. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11340-014-9900-4>
- [9] S. Coppeters, S. Cooreman, H. Sol, P. Van Houtte, and D. Debruyne, “Identification of the post-necking hardening behaviour of sheet metal by comparison of the internal and external work in the necking zone,” *J. Mater. Process. Technol.*, vol. 211, no. 3, pp. 545–552. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmatprotec.2010.11.015>
- [10] D. Lecompte, S. Cooreman, S. Coppeters, J. Vantomme, H. Sol, and D. Debruyne, “Parameter identification for anisotropic plasticity model using digital image correlation,” *Eur. J. Comput. Mech.*, vol. 18, no. 3–4, pp. 393–418. <https://doi.org/10.13052/EJCM.18.393-418>
- [11] A. Maček, B. Starman, N. Mole, and M. Halilović, “Calibration of Advanced Yield Criteria Using Uniaxial and Heterogeneous Tensile Test Data,” *Metals*, vol. 10, no. 4, p. 542. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met10040542>
- [12] S. Avril and F. Pierron, “General framework for the identification of constitutive parameters from full-field measurements in linear elasticity,” *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, vol. 44, no. 14, pp. 4978–5002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2006.12.018>
- [13] M. Grédiac and F. Pierron, “Applying the Virtual Fields Method to the identification of elasto-plastic constitutive parameters,” *Int. J. Plast.*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 602–627. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijplas.2005.04.007>
- [14] M. Rossi and F. Pierron, “Identification of plastic constitutive parameters at large deformations from three dimensional displacement fields,” *Comput. Mech.*, vol. 49, no. 1, pp. 53–71. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00466-011-0627-0>
- [15] A. Lattanzi, F. Barlat, F. Pierron, A. Marek, and M. Rossi, “Inverse identification strategies for the characterization of transformation-based anisotropic plasticity models with the non-linear VFM,” *Int. J. Mech. Sci.*, p. 105422. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmecsci.2020.105422>

- [16] B. Rahmani, I. Villemure, and M. Levesque, "Regularized virtual fields method for mechanical properties identification of composite materials," *Comput. Methods Appl. Mech. Eng.*, vol. 278, pp. 543–566. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2014.05.010>
- [17] L. Zhang *et al.*, "Verification of a virtual fields method to extract the mechanical properties of human optic nerve head tissues in vivo," *Biomech. Model. Mechanobiol.*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 871–887. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10237-016-0858-2>
- [18] A. Marek, F. M. Davis, and F. Pierron, "Sensitivity-based virtual fields for the non-linear virtual fields method," *Comput. Mech.*, vol. 60, no. 3, pp. 409–431. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00466-017-1411-6>
- [19] M. Rossi, F. Pierron, and M. Štamborská, "Application of the virtual fields method to large strain anisotropic plasticity," *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, vol. 97–98, pp. 322–335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2016.07.015>
- [20] A. Marek, F. M. Davis, J.-H. Kim, and F. Pierron, "Experimental Validation of the Sensitivity-Based Virtual Fields for Identification of Anisotropic Plasticity Models," *Exp. Mech.*, vol. 60, no. 5, pp. 639–664. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11340-019-00575-3>
- [21] M. Rossi, A. Lattanzi, L. Cortese, and D. Amodio, "An approximated computational method for fast stress reconstruction in large strain plasticity," *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, vol. 121, no. 14, pp. 3048–3065. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.6346>
- [22] H. Takizawa *et al.*, "Development of the User Subroutine Library 'Unified Material Model Driver for Plasticity (UMMDp)' for Various Anisotropic Yield Functions," *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.*, vol. 1063, no. 1, p. 012099. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1063/1/012099>
- [23] M. Halilović, M. Vrh, and B. Štok, "NICE—An explicit numerical scheme for efficient integration of nonlinear constitutive equations," *Math. Comput. Simul.*, vol. 80, no. 294–313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matcom.2009.06.030>
- [24] M. Vrh, M. Halilović, and B. Štok, "Improved explicit integration in plasticity," *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, vol. 81, no. 7, pp. 910–938. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.2737>
- [25] M. Halilović, M. Vrh, and B. Štok, "NICE h: a higher-order explicit numerical scheme for integration of constitutive models in plasticity," *Eng. Comput.*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 55–70. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00366-011-0243-9>
- [26] M. Halilovic, B. Starman, M. Vrh, and B. Stok, "A robust explicit integration of elasto-plastic constitutive models, based on simple subincrement size estimation," *Eng. Comput.*
- [27] T. J. R. Hughes and J. Winget, "Finite rotation effects in numerical integration of rate constitutive equations arising in large-deformation analysis," *Int. J. Numer. Methods Eng.*, vol. 15, no. 12, pp. 1862–1867. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.1620151210>
- [28] Y. Yamada, N. Yoshimura, and T. Sakurai, "Plastic stress-strain matrix and its application for the solution of elastic-plastic problems by the finite element method," *Int. J. Mech. Sci.*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 343–354. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-7403\(68\)90001-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-7403(68)90001-5)
- [29] M. C. Oliveira, J. L. Alves, B. M. Chaparro, and L. F. Menezes, "Study on the influence of work-hardening modeling in springback prediction," *Int. J. Plast.*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 516–543. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijplas.2006.07.003>
- [30] S. Yoon and F. Barlat, "Non-iterative stress integration method for anisotropic materials," *Int. J. Mech. Sci.*, vol. 242, p. 108003. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmecsci.2022.108003>
- [31] S. Bossuyt, "Optimized Patterns for Digital Image Correlation," in *Imaging Methods for Novel Materials and Challenging Applications, Volume 3*, H. Jin, C. Sciammarella, C. Furlong, and S. Yoshida, Eds., in Conference Proceedings of the Society for Experimental Mechanics Series. New York, NY: Springer, 2013, pp. 239–248. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4235-6_34